

METHOD FOR TREATMENT OF UROGENITAL CANDIDIASIS USING ULTRASONIC CAVITATION

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Abstract: This article refers to medicine, namely to gynecology can be used for treating urogenital candidiasis. Method provides effective treatment by cleaning tissues of protein debris, suppression of opportunistic microflora, improved rheological state of mucous membranes, stimulation of physiological processes of regeneration at normalization of functional metabolic status indicators of neutrophilic granulocytes of vaginal secretion, reduction of Schiff base values and normalization of free-radical oxidation processes in vaginal secretion.

Key words: chronic recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis, vaginal secretions, neutrophilic granulocytes, ultrasonic cavitation.

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Introduction. The treatments used to manage *Candida* infections vary substantially and are based on the anatomic location of the infection, the patients' underlying disease and immune status, the patients' risk factors for infection, the specific species of *Candida* responsible for infection, and, in some cases, the susceptibility of the *Candida* species to specific antifungal drugs.

There have been significant changes in the management of candidiasis in the last few years, particularly related to the appropriate use of echinocandins and expanded-spectrum azoles for candidemia, other forms of invasive candidiasis, and mucosal candidiasis.

Literary review. Over the past decade, the frequency of urogenital candidiasis has almost doubled. There is a tendency to the prevalence of recurrent forms of the disease.

Mushrooms of the genus *Candida* - conditionally pathogenic flora. So yeast-like fungi in 10% of cases are excreted from the mucous membrane of healthy people. With long-term chronic forms of candida infection, a certain kind of "symbiosis" is formed between the macroorganism and the conditionally pathogenic flora. According to many authors, candida is a marker of the immunodeficiency state of the body. The disease, as a rule, develops only in conditions of a decrease in the body's resistant forces.

Discussion and results. The basis of the pathogenesis of candida infection is a violation of T-cell immunity, its phagocytic link. The main type of cells that contribute to the elimination of yeast-like fungi from the body are neutrophils, macrophages and monocytes. Possessing pronounced phagocytic properties, neutrophils are included in the fight against infection earlier than specific means of protection, and thereby determine the further development of the

infectious process. Phagocytic cells can destroy both blastospores and pseudomycelial elements of candida fungi.

However, immunity in candida infection has a number of features that distinguish it from bacterial, viral and other fungal infections. A feature of immunity in candida infection is the ability of Candida fungi to resist the destruction of phagocytic cells: mycelium of yeast-like fungi secrete a specific substance that inhibits leukocyte chemotaxis; being phagocytosed, fungi block the bactericidal properties of neutrophils and are able to persist and multiply in them.

As a result, the rates of phagocytosis in candida infection to a certain extent depend not only on the functional ability of leukocytes, but also on the pathogenic properties of the fungi themselves. Therefore, standard methods for monitoring immunity indicators used for viral, bacterial and other fungal infections are not always a clear criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of treatment for candida infection.

Based on the features of the complex pathogenetic mechanism of candidiasis, where the leading role in the development of the disease is given to the state of the protective functions of the macroorganism itself, the appointment of only specific drugs, even highly effective ones, does not guarantee complete recovery.

Known methods of treating candidal infection based on the notion that chronic recurrent candidiasis is based on the failure of local cellular immunity, its phagocytic link. There is a large arsenal of immunomodulating agents, however, due to the lack of methods of sufficiently effective immunostimulation, long-term (up to a year) preventive courses of the drug Diflucan are prescribed. The disadvantages of this method are the long periods of treatment of the disease, as well as large course doses of antimycotic drugs, while the main pathogenetic link of the onset and development of candida infection is not eliminated.

The closest method is the treatment of chronic forms of urogenital candidiasis with an antimycotic fungistatic drug of systemic action Diflucan (fluconazol) from Pfizer. In chronic recurrent forms of urogenital candidiasis, dosages are selected individually under the control of elimination of yeast-like fungi from the body. Diflucan is prescribed at a dose of 150 mg once a week for 4 weeks.

The disadvantages of this method are high doses of the antimycotic drug, as well as a high percentage of relapses (up to 60%).

In this regard, it is advisable, along with the use of antimycotic drugs, to use methods of pathogenetic therapy that increase the defenses of the macroorganism.

An interferon inducer antiviral drug cycloferon recommended by Polisan, St. Petersburg (1996), is a drug that corrects the body's immune status, increases its protective properties, and increases the phagocytic activity of neutrophils. Recent studies have shown and pathogenetically substantiated the high efficacy of interferon and its inducers in the treatment of viral and bacterial infections. In immunodeficiency states of various etiologies, including fungal, in chronic forms of infection, cycloferon is recommended according to the following scheme: 250 mg iv or IM for 2 days in a row, then every other day from 10 to 15 injections. However, with urogenital candidiasis, this scheme is not effective enough.

The essence of the method: When making a diagnosis of chronic urogenital candidiasis, patients are initially given a course of immunomodulating therapy with cycloferon: 250 mg for

2 days in a row, then every other day iv administered under the control of immunological status assessment: indicators of T-cell immunity - CD₃, CD₄, CD₈, CD₁₆, the functional activity of neutrophils - NBT-test, the cation-lysosomal proteins, as well as specific indicators of the phagocytic activity of neutrophils by the method Coast and the wall, 1958 (determination of the phagocytic ability of neutrophils to culture fungi of the genus Candida).

To restore the phagocytic activity of neutrophils in relation to candida fungi, it took from 15 to 20 injections of cycloferon.

The final effect in the administration of immunomodulating agents in patients with candidiasis is the restoration of the phagocytic activity of neutrophils in relation to the patient's own fungal culture. Normalization of only general indicators of immunity and phagocytic ability of neutrophils, determined by standard research methods, cannot serve as a clear criterion for the effectiveness of immunostimulating therapy in this type of infection.

During our treatment, it was found that 15 injections of cycloferon are not always sufficient to restore the specific resistance of the body, therefore, in some cases (13.1%), up to 20 injections of the drug were used in patients, while to restore the general indicators of the T-cell immunity and The phagocytic activity of neutrophils with staphylococcus took from 10 to 15 injections of cycloferon.

Conclusion. A method of treating recurrent forms of urogenital candidiasis of women, based on the use of antimycrotic drugs and immunomodulating therapy, characterized in that they preliminarily conduct a course of immunomodulating therapy with cycloferon 250 mg for two days, then every other day intravenously - 15 to 20 injections until the phagocytic activity of neutrophils is restored in relation to fungi of the genus Candida, after which Diflucan is prescribed at 150 mg once a week for 2 to 3 weeks.

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